

ENDOSCOPIC AND VIDEO-THORACOSCOPIC INTERVENTIONS FOR ACUTE PLEURAL EMPYEMA IN CHILDREN

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Abstract. *The results of treatment of 117 patients aged 1 to 17 years with acute pleural empyema were analyzed. The effectiveness of early endoscopic interventions, such as sanitation bronchoscopy with short-term bronchial occlusion, as well as sanitation videothoracoscopy in the complex treatment of acute pleural empyema in children, was assessed.*

The results of the treatment showed the high clinical effectiveness of early simultaneous sanitation bronchoscopy with bronchial occlusion, as well as sanitation videothoracoscopy in the complex treatment of acute pleural empyema in children. The results obtained indicate the prospects for their widespread use, since they have high resolution and low invasiveness, prevent the development of serious complications and prevent the disease from becoming chronic.

Keywords: *children, acute pleural empyema, purulent-inflammatory diseases, lung tissue, respiratory failure, videothoracoscopy, sanitation bronchoscopy, bronchial occlusion.*

Relevance of the problem. Despite the successes achieved in the treatment of children with purulent-inflammatory diseases of the lungs, this problem remains far from being solved, which is largely due to the difficulty of determining the exact parameters of destructive changes in the lung tissue at various stages of the disease.

An important role in this is played by the fact that there is still no consensus on the issues of diagnosis, tactics and methods of performing surgical interventions in the early stages of the disease; this factor inevitably leads to various complications and functional disorders of both the respiratory system and the body in general [1, 4, 6]. Pleural empyema is a severe form of purulent-inflammatory process in the pleural cavity in children, the severity of which is due to manifestations of both respiratory failure and severe purulent intoxication. The progressive course of the disease is accompanied by inflammation of the visceral and parietal pleura, which in turn leads not only to pathological changes in the bronchopulmonary system, but also poses a serious risk of developing severe complications that put the patient's life at risk. The causative agents of diseases of the bronchopulmonary system are microorganisms and viruses; they participate in the development of suppuration processes in the lung tissue. The microbial agent enters the lungs by airborne droplets and hematogenously, causing pathological changes in the upper parts of the respiratory system, while local immunity is reduced and conditions are created for the penetration and proliferation of bacteria in the lower parts of the respiratory system, in particular in the lung tissue. Disruption of the microcirculation process in the lung tissue and at the level of bronchioles leads to functional dysfunction of the entire respiratory system, which is manifested by a weakening of the drainage function of the bronchial system and leads to respiratory failure. The accumulation of pus in the pleural cavity is in most cases the result of infection of the effusion against the background of a severe inflammatory process of various origins. Many researchers note that despite the improvement in the quality of diagnosis and the development of new methods for

treating acute pleural empyema in children, the transition of the disease to the purulent-fibrinous stage or to the stage of fibrin organization leads to blockage of the drainage system of the lungs, which requires puncture-drainage interventions of the pleural cavity and carrying out long-term conservative therapy with physiotherapeutic procedures [2, 8, 9, 12, 13, 14].

The widespread introduction of modern medical technologies into the clinical practice of thoracic surgery in childhood allowed the use of effective methods of bronchoscopic rehabilitation and videothoracoscopic surgical interventions in the treatment of many purulent-inflammatory diseases of the bronchopulmonary system in the early stages of their development, which in turn prevented the development of severe pulmonary pleural complications, in particular the development of acute pleural empyema [3, 5, 7, 10, 11]. Generally accepted puncture methods of treatment in children are effective only at the beginning of the disease. In the purulent-fibrinous stage of pleurisy with a long history of the disease, puncture and drainage of the pleural cavity in most cases do not give a pronounced positive effect. In the presence of negative dynamics, the absence of effect from long-term conservative treatment, aggravation of manifestations of respiratory failure due to chronic purulent intoxication and the formation of abscesses, pleural cavity sanitation, pneumolysis or lung decortication are indicated. Therefore, the early use of videothoracoscopic interventions in this cohort of patients is more effective, since this prevents the transition of acute pleural empyema to chronic.

The purpose of the study. To improve the results of treatment of acute pleural empyema in children, by early video thoracoscopic rehabilitation.

Research materials and methods. During the period from 2017 to 2024, 117 children aged 1 to 17 years with acute pleural empyema were hospitalized and treated at Pediatric Surgery Clinic of Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute. The distribution of patients by gender and age is presented in Table 1.

Table 1.

Distribution of patients by gender and age (N=117)

Age of patients	Gender				Total	
	Boys		Girls			
	abs	%	abs	%	abs	%
1-3 years old	30	25,6	22	19	52	44,6
4-7 years old	21	18	12	10,2	33	28,2
8-11 years old	10	8,5	4	3,4	14	11,9
12-17 years old	8	6,8	10	8,5	18	15,3
Total	69	59%	48	41%	117	100%

In the age aspect, the patients were divided into 4 groups, of which the group of patients aged 1 to 3 years prevailed, which amounted to 44.6% of children. The sex ratio showed that the most numerous group of patients with acute pleural empyema were boys - 69 (59%), respectively, there were 48 girls (41%). See also the data in the Table 1, which indicates the predominant number of hospitalized patients under the age of 7 years, which characterizes the adherence of this age group of patients to the susceptibility of infection and early pulmonary pleural complications, which are accompanied by severe course and rapid development of acute pleural empyema.

Depending on the prevalence of the purulent-inflammatory process in the pleural cavity, we revealed a significant difference in the involvement of the pathological process on the lesion side, the localization of acute pleural empyema in the right lung was detected in 62 (55.7%) patients, in the left lung – in 48 (38.9%), the involvement of both lungs in the pathological process was revealed in 7 (5.3%) patients (Diagram 1.).

Diagram 1.

The frequency and localization of the pathological process in the lungs

All hospitalized patients, regardless of age and duration of the disease, underwent chest X-ray examinations, ultrasound of the pleural cavity, MSCT of the chest organs, bronchoscopy and bronchography, clinical laboratory studies and bacteriological examination of effusion from the pleural cavity.

The results of the study.

In order to conduct randomized trials over a long period of time and compare the effectiveness of surgical treatment, our patients were divided into two groups to be compared. The first control group consisted of 57 (48.7%) patients who underwent punctures and drainage of the pleural cavity, as well as sanitization bronchoscopy (if necessary, bronchococclusion), as an independent method of surgical treatment. The second main group, with 60 (51.3%) patients, consisted of patients who, in addition to punctures and drainage of the pleural cavity, sanitization bronchoscopy with bronchococclusion, also underwent early thoracoscopic intervention (Table 2).

Table 2

Distribution of patients with acute pleural empyema into comparison groups

Age	main group (n=60)		control group (n=57)	
	abs.	%	abs.	%
1-3 years old	27	45	25	43,8
4-7 years old	17	28,3	16	28,1
8-11 years old	9	15	5	8,8
12-17 years old	7	11,7	11	19,3
Total	60	100%	57	100%

It should be noted that the determination of etiological factors and causes leading to the development of acute pleural empyema in patients contributes to the correct pathogenetic choice of tactics, timing and methods of treatment. To this end, purulent-inflammatory processes detected in the lung and pleural cavity were evaluated according to the generally recognized classification of thoracic surgeons of the American Association, on the basis of which our patients were divided into the following 3 stages: I - exudative stage (28 patients), II - purulent-fibrinous stage (62 patients), III - stage of organization fibrin (27 patients). The causes of acute pleural empyema in 18 (15.4%) cases were infection and suppuration of the pleural cavity due to a lung abscess, while

an abscess breakthrough into the bronchi was detected in 27 (23.1%) patients. Pulmonary pleural complications in the form of exudative pleurisy were detected in 19 (16.2%) cases, pyothorax and pyopneumothorax in 53 (45.3%) patients.

Diagnostic and therapeutic puncture of the pleural cavity was performed in all 117 patients with acute pleural empyema, it was performed according to a standard procedure under local anesthesia, the puncture point was the V-VII intercostal space along the mid-axillary line, the resulting fluid from the pleural cavity was sent to the bacteriological laboratory. With the ineffectiveness of puncture treatment in 53 (45.3%) cases, drainage of the pleural cavity was performed with daily washing with decasan solution and administration of antibiotics, depending on sensitivity to the isolated microflora. Puncture-drainage interventions were effective in 32 (27.3%) cases in patients with the I-exudative stage of pleurisy.

However, in 60 (51.3%) patients of the main group with pyothorax, pyopneumothorax and fibrothorax, performing only puncture-drainage interventions turned out to be insufficient, since a significant progression of the purulent-inflammatory process in the lungs and pleural cavity in these patients contributed to a weakening of the compensatory and adaptive capabilities of child's body and the development of severe respiratory disorders with hypoventilation and lung atelectasis, the formation of bronchopleural fistulas. In this contingent of patients, for the full restoration of airway patency and stimulation of impaired bronchial drainage function, sanitization bronchoscopy was performed simultaneously, if necessary with bronchococclusion, as well as videothoracoscopy.

Intraoperative videothoracoscopic images of pleural empyema before and after

The effectiveness of simultaneous bronchoscopy and videothoracoscopic interventions turned out to be significantly higher compared with puncture-drainage interventions. In this group, 38 (32.5%) patients with purulent fibrinous stage of acute pleural empyema underwent thoracoscopic sanitation of the pleural cavity with removal of fibrin deposits on the surface of the visceral and parietal pleural leaflets and subsequent drainage. In 22 (18.8%) patients at the stage of fibrin organization, videothoracoscopic dissection of adhesions, emptying of non-drainable purulent cavities, as well as lung decortication were performed.

Conclusion. Thus, the conducted studies allowed us to conclude that bronchoscopic rehabilitation and videothoracoscopic interventions are more effective in the complex treatment of acute pulmonary empyema in children. The advantage of these techniques is minimally invasive

intervention, alternative to open thoracotomy, minimization of hospitalization time, prevention of the transition of the disease to a chronic form of the disease.

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